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TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF MEDICAL AND PEDIATRIC FACULTIES OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY IN RADIATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE

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Annotation: The analysis of the results of the use of active forms and methods of teaching in the educational process, a rating system for evaluating educational and other activities of students to improve the effectiveness of their radiation and environmental training, it was found that the use of active methods and forms of training in teaching radiation and environmental medicine, as well as a rating system for assessing students' knowledge increase their success in studying and mastering. They solve a number of educational, educational and developmental tasks at the same time, making the learning process interesting and creative.

Keywords: active forms of education, educational process, radiation and environmental medicine

ПОДГОТОВКА СТУДЕНТОВ ЛЕЧЕБНОГО И ПЕДИАТРИЧЕСКОГО ФАКУЛЬТЕТОВ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ВУЗА ПО РАДИАЦИОННО-ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЕ

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Аннотация: Проведен анализ результатов применения в учебном процессе активных форм и методов обучения, рейтинговой системы оценки учебной и другой деятельности студентов для повышения эффективности их радиационно-экологической подготовки, установлено, что использование активных методов и форм обучения в преподавании радиационной и экологической медицины, а также рейтинговой системы оценки знаний студентов повышают их успешность в изучении и освоении данного предмета и одновременно решают ряд учебных, воспитательных и развивающих задач, делая процесс обучения интересным и творческим.

Keywords: активные формы обучения, учебный процесс, радиационная и экологическая медицина

Relevance. The presence of a huge arsenal of xenobiotic chemical and radioactive substances of various physicochemical properties and biological activity, as well as their large-scale application in various fields of modern man's activity, contribute to the formation of a tense radiation and environmental situation in his environment. The increased aggressiveness of the external environment, the contamination of the internal environment of the body, the wide prevalence of environmentally caused health disorders in children and adults indicate the relevance and need to improve the quality of radiation and environmental training of medical specialists who are able to effectively monitor the safe functioning of people and the preservation of their health [1].

It is necessary to train a new level of specialists capable of skillfully analyzing, generalizing and systematizing the available information, generating new knowledge, developing effective methods of diagnosis and treatment of diseases, putting into practice the results of scientific research, can only provide innovative education in medicine [2].

Goal. Analysis of the results of the use of active forms and methods of teaching in the educational process, a rating system for evaluating educational and other activities of students to improve the effectiveness of their radiation and environmental training.

Materials and methods of research. Some aspects of the organization of the educational process and the results of the final control

of students' knowledge in radiation and environmental medicine at the medical and pediatric faculties of the medical University were studied.

Results and their discussion. Currently, radiation and environmental training of future doctors of medical and pediatric profile at Grodno State Medical University is carried out at the Department of Radiation Diagnostics and Therapy in accordance with the requirements of the educational standard and standard curricula and is implemented by giving lectures, conducting laboratory classes, students performing guided independent work and involving them in educational and research activities.

The study of radiation and environmental medicine, which is taught in the 2nd year in two semesters, is allocated 136 hours, including classroom – 86 hours, of which lectures – 20 hours, seminars – 66 hours. The form of the final certification of knowledge is a differentiated credit. Both traditional and modern educational and information resources are used for teaching students (computer presentations of lectures and a number of questions in laboratory classes voiced in connection with COVID-19), interactive resources in the local computer network of the university and the Internet.

Among the active forms of learning, effective and well-perceived by students are dialogical forms of building seminars in the form of educational discussions and round tables. Experience shows that the methods of educational discussions and round tables significantly improve and consolidate knowledge, increase the volume of assimilation of new information, develop students' ability to argue, prove their point of view, listen and take into account the opinions of others.

Students are greatly interested in environmental workshops, where modern equipment is used to study the etiological factors of health disorders in environmental diseases. The role of the teacher is in the skillful organization of the educational process, consulting and final evaluation of the work performed.

The solution of situational tasks in the classroom includes an assessment of the etiological factor, preliminary diagnosis, pathogenesis, algorithms for the treatment and prevention of environmental and radiation pathology; forms a practice-oriented orientation in teaching, the basics of clinical thinking of students.

Much attention is paid to student science, which contributes to the formation of a student's creative and creative personality. Many of them participate in the implementation of scientific research on radiation and environmental issues, successfully make presentations at regularly organized by the department of educational-thematic and scientific-practical conferences. Every year, the department holds Olympiads in the studied disciplines, reviews and contests of videos and small media on pathogenesis, prevention of environmental diseases and radiation pathology. Their winners have advantages in the final assessment of knowledge, which is carried out according to the rating system and takes into account both educational and various independent cognitive activities of students.

Analyzing the academic performance on the subject at the medical and pediatric faculties in recent years, it should be noted a constant increase in the average score, especially significant among students of the pediatric profile (6.5–7.8 points, respectively). In 2019-1022 academic years, the average scores on the differentiated test in radiation and environmental medicine were, respectively, for students of the Faculty of Medicine: 6.9; 7.0; 8.1; 8.2 and 8.1; for students of the Faculty of Pediatrics: 6.7; 6.9; 8.0; 7.8 and 8.1.

Conclusion. Thus, the use of active methods and forms of education in teaching radiation and environmental medicine, as well as a rating system for assessing students' knowledge, increase their success in studying and mastering this subject and simultaneously solve a number of educational, educational and developmental tasks, making the learning process interesting and creative.

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